

careables.org

D2.4

Insight

Report (incl.

Reproductions)

Date
December 2020

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Careables.org is managed by the Made4You project and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 780298.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

During the course of the Careables project, we co-designed tailored solutions and made them openly accessible to others. This report shares insights within three focal points: Experiences and learnings made in the context of **moving events** from the **physical to the virtual**, **replication stories centered around the COVID-19 pandemic**, and acquired knowledge around the topic of **parametric solutions and accessibility**.

We found that, as online sessions can be more exhausting, it is helpful to switch between different modus operandi. In moving from physical to online we made good experiences with dividing the sessions into inputs, breakout sessions, and working on a digital whiteboard turned out to help against digital fatigue.

- Big advantage: Possibility to take part in events regardless of the physical location.
- Digital divide: No access to technology or equipment. Not everyone has access to a fast computer, unlimited internet.
- Do you have to sign up for / and or download applications in order to take part?
- Some tools are difficult to control through voice based interfaces.
- As only one person can speak at a time, consider moving to breakout rooms for having more engaged and engaging discussions in smaller (sub-)groups.
- Online can be more exhausting, so don't calculate the same time meeting time as in physical meetings.

As for replications connected to COVID-19, it showed that Fablabs and makerspaces are great places for quick innovation and initial production. In the case of face shields, iterative solutions focused on adaptability and easy production. In a second phase, injection molding was used to produce higher quantities. Now you can buy face shields virtually at every corner. The core strength of creating and producing careables in Fablabs and makerspaces lays in highly individualized custom solutions,

- On the Design side, people were working on optimizing the designs for faster printing.
- Others were creating 3D printing farms to parallelize the printing and to enable continuous machine use.
- Engineers from Beuth University for Applied Science and others created an injection mold for producing even larger quantities in industrial facilities.
- Slowly general industrial production caught up.

Parametric solutions are of high value for careables, as they often have to be exactly fitted to the body, wheelchair, etc. Here we found that web interfaces have the lowest barrier for the users, while finding skilled designers that can create parametric solutions, ideally with free/libre open-source software (FLOSS) computer-aided design (CAD) tools remains difficult. Here we would like to see a bigger focus on FLOSS tools in higher design education.

- Parametric modelling requires special designers who are accustomed to systems thinking and have experience in creating adaptable models.
- The software tools taught in higher education are often proprietary, whereas FLOSS CAD software solutions lower the barriers for potential contributors significantly.
- From the user perspective, even having to download and install a specific software like OpenSCAD can feel challenging, so web interface solutions or chat-bot interfaces provide a better UX.
- Generating system toolchains for larger badges of individualized careables can pay off in terms of reusability and scaling efforts.

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List of abbreviations

AH	Agile Heap e.V. / Prototypes
CR	Care recipient
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
FLOSS	Free/Libre Open Source Software
HP	Healthcare professional
KUL	KU Leuven
LP	Lead partner
OPEN	OpenDot
TOG	Together to Go Foundation
UX	User Experience
VOCT	Visual Online Collaboration Tools
WAAG	WAAG society
WEV	Wevolver
WP	Work Package
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation – ZSI

1. Introduction

This report is to share insights from the co-development processes and replications that happened in the Careables project. Our repository of open healthcare solutions is growing, and we added a section under the COVID-19 tag¹ to reflect the solutions that are directly connected to the ongoing pandemic crisis. During the course of the project, we had to move the co-creation and replication sessions from the Fablabs and makerspaces into the virtual.

We will share some insights from physical co-design sessions, and will then highlight learnings from hybrid event formats, as well as online events. Furthermore, we will give examples of take-aways in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and the production efforts in an early response situation,

Lastly, we focus on the creation of parametric solutions, the key requirements, possible pitfalls, and pathways to low-barrier user interaction. Here we also highlight a successful Kickstarter campaign.

2. Insights from Online Co-Creation Events

In this report, we also want to share and highlight learnings and experiences from moving co-design and co-creation events from previously happening in Fablabs and makerspaces, for a great part to the online world - as a result of the requirements emerging through the pandemic situation. We start with sharing learnings from physical co-design sessions, exemplified by learnings from Waag.

Learnings from Physical Co-Design Sessions

First hand experience report from Waag:

“Our learnings from the sessions at Waag were that it works. Bringing people with healthcare challenges, healthcare professionals, designers, and makers together really enables a fruitful context in which open healthcare solutions (careables) can be co-designed and co-produced. However, this does not happen by itself. It really takes time for people to

¹ <https://www.welder.app/careables?tags=COVID-19>

get to know each other, but especially learn to experience the added value of one person. Participants need to see what the skills and expertise of the other team members are for a good collaboration.

In Waag we've also experimented with single evenings to work on a specific careable. This is also a possibility, however, those evenings remain at the level of advanced brainstorming: some great ideas were presented, but there was not enough time to go into details for the solutions."

One general learning is that a main outcome of the co-creation and co-development sessions, additionally to the creation of a careable, is the process and the experience that each participant has through working on a specific solution in a diverse team. This experience of learning other perspectives and gaining insights is very valuable. We believe that the participants share their learnings with others well beyond the actual events, also because some participants joined several events and/or introduced us to new participants.

While regular meet-up events are good for brainstorming and introducing people to the general concepts of Careables, longer-running dedicated co-creation formats have worked better for us in terms of successful co-creation and co-development of careables. The commitment has generally been higher in the extended formats. We have mostly concentrated on primarily user-centered development. Identifying new technological developments, and working on putting them to use by working with people that can use them as a careable, could be a way to excite a more technically savvy group of developers.

Thoughts on documentation

First hand experience report from Waag:

"Documentation is always tricky. In the first two Make Health prototyping series that we have organised, the platform was not really functional yet. So we had a lot of issues documenting the work of the teams.

In our experience, the documentation is always a hassle. We pointed out to our participants that they should do it, make sure that one team member is 'head of documentation', and make sure that there were enough photos taken.

But having documentation is very insightful and a starting point for prototyping, especially when replicating a careable. In Amsterdam, we organised the replication with student teams (second and third-year students at the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences). They formed teams and could choose one of the careables to work on. They started

with the documentation and orientation on the user, to get a better understanding of what is needed. The student teams didn't replicate one-on-one, but they elaborated on the prototype as it was. Several teams were supported by the initiators of the careables (like Debby - White cane² or Lyndsey - Qualifire, a Multiple sclerosis [MS] self-management tool.

Each team documented their work in a new careable. It depends on the background of the students how they worked: some of them had a product design background and were able to design the careables. Others had a more technical background and spent their time on a functional sensor."

In more general terms, and to summarize the experience in all the makerspaces and Fablabs involved, it is challenging to encourage participants of a co-development process, to put effort into the documentation. This has to do with the limited time resources of the participants, and is also due to the fact that documentation is the last step in a co-development process.

Nonetheless, telling the participants that this is the only way to a) **share their solutions** and b) **to enable others to replicate** and build on the existing solutions, helps participants to understand the context better.

Presumably, as the creation and co-development process requires a lot of trial and error, the focus during the creation process is often more on finding a solution for the subparts of the complex problem, than on documentation. Development processes are often non-trivial to plan and execute, and the positive stimulation of having solved a tricky problem is often higher than the task of creating good documentation.

² <https://www.lightupcane.com/en/>

Hybrid Event: Open Health HACKademy #3

As an example case, we use the third iteration of our format Open Health Hackademy organised by Agile Heap e.V./Prototypes in collaboration with our partner be-able e.V., which has in total run three times during the course of the Careables project. A fourth event is already in the planning (see Figure 1).

The graphic is a three-column layout with a blue, green, and dark grey background respectively. Each column contains text and a button.

Your challenge for the HACKademy	Work out solutions	Mentors and input providers wanted!
<p>Are you experiencing a hurdle and feeling excluded from certain activities? Do you belong to the risk group and need a tool to take better care of yourself in the corona crisis situation?</p> <p>You can submit your challenge for the Open Health HACKademy # 4 and for a collaboration via MatchMyMaker here.</p>	<p>Register as a maker, designer, health expert or supporter for Hackademy # 4 or for matching via MatchMyMaker.</p> <p>Become part of an inclusive team.</p>	<p>We are looking for people who would like to donate time and support us and our teams as mentors, input providers, helpers, coaches or social media heroes.</p> <p>Become part of the Open Health HACKademy # 4 team.</p>
Submit a challenge	Work out solutions	Donate time

Figure 1: Call for Open Health Hackademy #4

While we had previously experimented with different durations of the event, ranging from two weeks to two months, this time we did most of the co-design processes in regular online sessions, which lead to the final phase which included production and meeting possibilities in a physical fabrication laboratory. The Beuth University of Applied Sciences Berlin³ volunteered to host us for this third Hackademy. Some participants were able to join physically while others attended this last phase online as well. In the following, we are able to share some experiences from this hybrid format.

³ <https://www.beuth-hochschule.de/>

Figure 2: Hybrid event, partly online and partly in a physical space

The hybrid event form can be seen temporally on the one hand, the first several weeks online, and the final phase in person at a physical location. Additionally, this final phase was hybrid in itself, as we were trying to create a productive situation within the fabrication laboratory, while at the same time including the other (online) participants in a meaningful way. These remotely attending participants were mostly spread over Germany.

In order to understand the challenge we first explain the basic structure: The Open Health Hackademy is organized around case providers, usually people with a need for an individualized solution to improve their life.

Case providers

Case providers have an essential role within the project. Case providers often provide the initial idea, the individual challenge to develop a careable for. They can provide continuous input and give feedback - ideally during the whole development process. Additionally, case providers are usually fulfilling their individual roles in the team.

We learned that in cases where the case provider has not been available during the entire process, team motivation can suffer, and the development route can become fuzzy. Additionally, other team members might get the impression that

the project they are working on is not important to the person one is designing and developing with and for.

On the contrary, deeply involved case providers can boost motivation. Additionally to the artifacts created, this experience of working together in diverse teams helps to emphasize across different cultures, disciplines, ways of working and thinking, to name a few.

Learning: If the case-provider, or alternatively an involved care provider, can not commit to joining, one should carefully outweigh if this can still create a meaningful experience for the rest of the team.

Methodological Framework

The Hackademy format includes elements and inputs from Design Thinking⁴, a human-centered design process, which is centered around an iterative process, which is structured into five phases:

- **Empathize**
- **Define**
- **Ideate**
- **Prototype**
- **Test**

As these phases are non-linear, they can be repeated, and run in parallel. Sticky notes have become a visual marker for design thinking processes, they are often depicted to show creative development processes. The key advantages of sticky notes are the fact that participants can ideate in parallel. Everyone involved can use a given time-frame to write down or draw ideas and express thoughts and the moderator can collect and rearrange these sticky notes to structure and cluster them accordingly in a team process. Here a proprietary software as a service (SAAS) product came handily into play. Miro⁵, the service previously known as Realtime-Board, is an "An Online Visual Collaboration Platform for Teamwork" as they describe themselves. In Miro, several people can access an online whiteboard and collaboratively add and edit the contents (see Figure 2).

This enabled us to prepare exercises and worksheets in advance, similar to the equivalent worksheets for physical workshops. We found that being able to switch between different modes of interaction kept participants engaged. We changed between frontal inputs as video calls, breakout sessions (will be described further in the video conference section), and the sessions in Miro.

⁴ <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/design-thinking>

⁵ <https://miro.com/>

Through the visual components and the possibility to place and rearrange elements in a two-dimensional plane, the visual online collaboration tool (VOCT) resembles the process of working with sticky notes (and other graphical elements like sketches, photos and icons to visualize processes in a co-creative manner), on a physical whiteboard more closely than e.g. shared online documents.

Figure 3: Miro Board

On a side note, shared online documents based on e.g. Etherpad can also be a useful tool when sitting in a shared physical space with using laptops or alike while listening to a presentation. In this way, all participants can add additional information and thoughts to a shared document without interrupting the presentation. This multi-modality and concurrency appears to help some people to stay engaged in situations and enables them to share-second order thoughts.

While the use of VOCTs was widely adopted by many of the participants, accessibility-wise the graphical interface of VOCTs can make it hard or impossible for some individuals to participate. One participant was e.g. using a system of speech commands to navigate the cursor, which can be used in exceptional cases, but not to use VOCTs. Here it would be necessary to implement other interfaces.

As open source hardware (OSHW) development ideally uses free/libre open-source software (FLOSS) solutions, to ensure accessibility also from an economical point of view, we were looking for alternatives to Miro and came across Spacedeck, which we are now testing for smaller collaborative development projects. For a comparison see Table 1.

Visual Online Collaboration Tools (VOCT)

Miro (formally called Realtime-Board)	Miro worked quite well, as Design Thinking methods rely heavily on sticky notes. Miro provides digital sticky notes and one can prepare worksheets in advance.	Proprietary
Spacedeck	As we only came across spacedeck.com after the event, we were not able to use it in these cases. Spacedeck looks promising and can be used as a collaborative visual online tool. The workflow is a bit different, but the closest to our requirements in the open source self-hostable software solution space.	Open Source Software Self-hostable

Table 1: Visual Online Collaboration Tools (VOCT)

Video Conferencing Tools

While working in visual online collaboration tools (VOCTs) sharing the video feed of all participants can lead to overheating processors, so we recommend switching to audio only, while mainly working in a different browser tab. At the start and the end of a session, it can help to see each other's faces in order to relate to the group. The main advantage of breakout sessions is that it can be a more personal and focussed space for discussions. Here participants can talk more freely. Breakout sessions are good for group work, brainstorming, and alike. As people dislike speaking in front of bigger groups, splitting into breakout sessions can lower the barrier of asking questions and it creates a more interactive setting. We mainly used Big Blue Button (BBB), Jitsi, and Zoom. BBB is widely used in schools, especially where data privacy concerns prevail. We found BBB to be a great alternative to Zoom. BBB also offers breakout rooms and even shared notes. Jitsi is also a great communication tool, and one can create separate rooms if one wants to resemble breakout functionality, but there is no interface to administer who is being sent into breakout rooms. Please also refer to Table 2.

Video Conferencing Solutions

<p>Big Blue Button</p>	<p>In the first sessions, we used a Big Blue Button (BBB) instance provided by Beuth Hochschule. Despite some minor drawbacks, the experience was good.</p> <p>The functionality of breakout rooms was used for working in smaller groups.</p>	<p>Open Source Software Self-hostable</p>
<p>JITSI</p>	<p>Jitsi was a possibility for the teams to have a video conferencing tool available whenever they wanted to use it. Jitsi was provided by the Beuth University of Applied Science.</p>	<p>Open Source Software Self-hostable</p>
<p>ZOOM</p>	<p>The simultaneous combination of a video conferencing tool and the visual online collaboration tool (VOCT) led to a high processor load on some computers of the participants in the case of BBB. As a result, we switched to ZOOM during the event.</p>	<p>Proprietary</p>

Table 2: Video conferencing tools used

Key points to consider

- Big advantage: Possibility to take part in events regardless of the physical location.
- Digital divide: No access to technology or equipment. Not everyone has access to a fast computer, unlimited internet.
- Do you have to sign up for / and or download applications in order to take part?
- Some tools are difficult to control through a voice-based interface
- As only one person can speak at a time, consider moving to breakout rooms for having more engaged and engaging discussions in smaller (sub-)groups.
- Online can be more exhausting, so don't calculate the same time meeting time as in physical meetings.

3. COVID-19 replication stories

As highlighted in the previous section the COVID-19 pandemic led to changes in the formats of our co-creation and co-design sessions. In this section, we want to highlight some learnings from the creation of careables by ourselves and the community. Within the first wave, there was an urgent need for personal protection equipment (PPE), both in the medical and the private sector. Many people wanted to contribute by finding solutions, helping to produce, to distribute, and to inform⁶. Especially the terrible crisis in Italy during the first wave has drowned Fablabs and Makerspaces into helping by creating, producing, and distributing.

Different contexts

Before focusing on the COVID-19 cases, some general learnings on replication. From our replication efforts in Brazil, we learned anecdotally that the group in Olinda was at first interested in replicating the mobile wheelchair ramp⁷. However, it turned out that the height of the sidewalk cornerstones in Brazil varies much more than in Germany. So wheelchair users in Brazil would need an entirely different solution; a ramp that is adjustable in height.

Design for Adaptability

Adaptability is of course a general theme in making and adapting our highly individualized careables. There is always the question of exact measurements, and how to adjust for good fit and comfortability. On the one hand, it is possible to design for adaptability (compare Figure 4), on the other one can create parametric designs, where the taken measurements are used as input to generate a custom 3D model. If one creates a one-size-fits-all model, one can produce many e.g. by using a 3D printing farm, or by moving on to injection molding processes to produce large quantities of the same solution. In this case, one does not need to take further individual measurements, and one can also imagine Producing them in size categories, where the individual adaptation is a matter of the “smart” construction.

⁶ Please also compare the COVID-19 paper that has been submitted to Frontiers in Sociology (the paper is provided as an Annex in the deliverable D4.3)

⁷ <https://www.welder.app/careables.org/3d.printed.wheelchair-ramp.for.one.step>

Figure 4: Design for Adaptability: While PLA material is quite rigid, this wavy shape adapts well to different head measurements.

Face Shields and Facemasks

During the first wave of the pandemic, protective gear for medical staff was not available in the numbers needed, Makerspaces and Fablabs were approached to help with the situation. In a collaborative effort, the production capabilities e.g. in Berlin were being combined to print up to 5000 face shield holders.

- On the Design side, people were working on optimizing the designs for faster printing.
- Others were creating 3D printing farms to parallelize the printing and to enable continuous machine use.
- Engineers from Beuth University for Applied Science and others created an injection mold for producing even larger quantities in industrial facilities.
- Slowly general industrial production caught up.

Similar efforts were being taken for producing masks in large quantities. Project Carola⁸ was an open-source project aiming at the creation of mask producing facilities in containers that could easily be shipped to regions with a need for facemask supplies.

⁸ <https://www.projectcarola.org/en/about-the-project/>

Earsavers

A subsequent need that arose were so-called Earsavers⁹. Professionals having to wear face masks all day can improve the comfort of wearing as the ears might become sore from the constant rubbing. The Earsavers can also improve the fit and airtightness of the masks.

Other designs

At the time of writing this report, we have **37** entries of COVID-19 related careables¹⁰ on our platform. Further examples include different designs of door openers, some of them being permanently attached to the door, others can be brought as a personal item. Working with the same idea of not having to touch surfaces there is a Push Button Tool for Kids¹¹, or a Tap Adapter¹², to turn on and off the water of a faucet with your elbow,

Key Learnings from COVID-19 reproductions

Learnings from these efforts are:

- Makerspaces and Fablabs can co-create solutions and optimize the designs for specific needs.
- Makerspaces and Fablabs can help overcome temporary production capacity gaps.
- Industrial mass production is still significantly more efficient in producing large quantities of the same product.
- Individualized solutions with the need for exact measurements are a good fit for development and production in Makerspaces and Fablabs.

4. Parametric Solutions and Accessibility

Parametric design implementation requires additional effort on the side of the original creator. This involves setting meaningful parametric ranges, ensuring that the objects do not break.

⁹ <https://www.welder.app/careables.org/posterior.harness/>

¹⁰ <https://www.welder.app/careables?tags=COVID-19>

¹¹ <https://www.welder.app/careables.org/push.button.tool.for.kids/>

¹² <https://www.welder.app/careables.org/tap.adapter/>

Experiences from Waag: Regarding the parametric designs and careables: you need to have a thorough understanding of 3D modelling to be able to design a parametric careable. This is really for people with a (product) design background or modelling skills. Within Waag, we developed one parametric careable: the pill box. It was designed by one of our interns - Sjoerd, together with Rutger. Their biggest challenge was to translate the needs of the user into the parametric model. They started with a first meeting with the user, to understand what the challenge was, that she experienced. Based on that first talk, they started to design and prototype. The first prototypes did not match the needs of the user, and they had to iterate multiple times to address the needs properly.

Still, it was great that they were able to make prototypes relatively easy, based on the parametric model. Each prototype helped the user to express her needs better, resulting in a functional pill box that she could use.

At **Fablab Berlin**, we created a parametric version of Glifo 2.0, parametric-glifo¹³, based on the original design files and used a FLOSS tool called OpenSCAD¹⁴ with a customizer functionality to scale and place the parts. This parameterized model can be relatively easily adapted, without special programming skills, as the customizer function provides access to the variables in a user-friendly way. Working with an imported STL¹⁵ can be a possibility to make 3D models adaptable, even though the original creators might have used proprietary CAD software and have not shared their original files. Creating parametric models from dissecting STL files is sort of a hack and requires programming skills in order to use OpenSCAD. Ideally, the original designers use open tools in the design process, An example is Kaepsele¹⁶ where a parametric solution has been directly created with OpenSCAD.

¹³ <https://github.com/nielek2/parametric-glifo>

¹⁴ <https://www.openscad.org/>

¹⁵ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/STL_\(file_format\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/STL_(file_format))

¹⁶ <https://www.welder.app/antonia.reden/kaepsele/>

Figure 5: Parametric OpenSCAD model of the Glifo with customizer functionality

Nevertheless, even on the side of potential replicators, the barrier to downloading, installing, and familiarizing oneself with an unfamiliar piece of software to enter the individual measurements can be perceived as high.

Ideally web-based interface to adapt parametric designs

One of the key learnings is that ideally one creates a web-based interface to guide through the process of measuring and then have a backend that creates the printable STL according to the measurements and provides it through the web interface for direct download. We created a proof-of-concept using OpenSCAD but did not deploy it yet for security reasons. One needs a dedicated server running OpenSCAD and forwards the built parameters directly through parameters to an instance of the software.

This toolchain is very promising as it can be self-hosted and based entirely on FLOSS, but it requires the designers to use OpenSCAD to create their models. Making FLOSS a requirement in higher education could help to learn alternative tools: “Learn image editing - not Photoshop®.”

OpenDot Kickstarter campaign for replication and configuration

“Now we can develop an online configurator that allows anyone to customize their Glifo, adapting it to their needs or tastes. We want people to be able to choose the size, angle, and color, using a simple and accessible interface.”

Open Dot, from the Kickstarter Campaign Website

Figure 6: Current version of the Glifo

The Glifo tool is a custom made writing aid, currently in its third iteration (compare Figure 6), that helps children with disabilities achieve autonomy in writing and drawing. During the successful Kickstarter campaign, 170 people pledged 5.555€ to support the replication and distribution of customized Glifos to children.

Figure 7: Kickstarter-backed online configurator (mock-up) - expected realization March 2021

A major challenge is the logistics involved in individualized bigger production batches. Collecting the individual measurements and ensuring that everyone becomes their custom product can be best solved by a database system, which collects the required information through a web interface and also automatically creates the 3D models for reproduction. In this case, OpenDot opted for an external 3D printing service to ensure the consistent quality of the prints.

The approach of providing a web-based interface for customization seemed also like the easiest from the user perspective. By giving clear instructions (compare Figure 7) of, choosing the left or right hand, how to measure the children's hand and inputting this information into the interface the individual product can be generated and made ready for production.

Additionally, aspects like embedding the child's name and or the company logo of the sponsor are options that can be realized fairly easily once one creates the entire service toolchain.

Parametric Modelling Key Points

- Parametric modelling requires special designers who are accustomed to systems thinking and have experience in creating adaptable models.
- The software tools taught in higher education are often proprietary, whereas FLOSS CAD software solutions lower the barriers for potential contributors significantly.
- From the user perspective, even having to download and install a specific software like OpenSCAD can feel challenging, so web interface solutions or chat-bot interfaces provide a better UX.
- Generating system toolchains for larger badges of individualized Careables can pay off in terms of reusability and scaling efforts.

5. Conclusions

The pandemic situation has led us to look into careables that can be used to prevent or slow down the spread of the virus. Here the community has come up with various solutions and derivatives. Especially in the context of improving and adapting designs, the Open Hardware approach shows positive effects, as people can directly build on the solutions of others. Moreover, the use of FLOSS CAD solutions can further reduce the barriers for contributors.

The production and scaling efforts have shown where Fablabs and Makerspaces are useful. This is especially the case in early response production and iterative product development. Also Design for Adaptability can help to make a careable fitting to different users.

Industrial processes remain favourable for mass production. Injection molding has the disadvantage that molds are expensive to produce in the first place, but production time and price are far better at high quantities.

Moving co-design, co-creation, and replication to online sessions has brought the advantages of being able to include participants in different locations. Also, we developed processes that can be used in further workshops and events. These learnings will also be helpful for other online sessions.

Advancing further into the direction of designing parametric solutions and providing low-barrier access for users to adapt careables according to their specific needs and measurements has been worthwhile, and can be expanded on in the near future.